

EFFECTIVE METHODS OF INCREASING SCHOOLCHILDREN'S INTEREST IN FOLK ART THROUGH NATIONAL CHILDREN'S FOLK SONGS

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Abstract: The article discusses the importance of Uzbek children's folk songs in developing children's creative abilities and the effective use of effective methods for instilling love and interest in folk art in primary school students.

Key words: folklore, children's songs, creativity, national traditions, methodology, emotionality, features of folk songs

Music education occupies a large place and importance in the process of teaching and educating high school students in many countries of the world. Musical education is formed and implemented on the basis of the national consciousness and thinking of this state, folk traditions, and the requirements of the time. One of the priority tasks facing our society today is educating the younger generation to be healthy both spiritually and physically. The younger generation, brought up in the spirit of maturity, will become a pillar of progress and development of our society by tomorrow. Primary education is an important stage in a child's development that lays the foundation for lifelong learning and personal growth. In recent years, teachers and researchers have recognized the importance of including cultural elements in the curriculum to enrich the educational experience and ensure comprehensive student development. With its rich cultural heritage and vibrant folk music traditions, the Uzbek people offer a unique opportunity to explore the role of traditional songs in developing the creative abilities of primary school students. Uzbek folk songs occupy a special place in the cultural fabric of the people and have served for centuries as a means of self-expression, narration, and national celebration. These songs, passed down from generation to generation, embody the common wisdom, values, and traditions of Uzbek inheritance society and open a window into the country's rich cultural heritage. In the context of primary education, Uzbek folk songs are a rich resource for educators who seek to engage students in meaningful exploration of their cultural heritage through the development of creative, critical thinking, and socio-cultural awareness.

Literature on the integration of folk music, and particularly Uzbek folk songs, into primary education shows its profound impact on various aspects of children's development. Scientists and teachers have extensively studied the

cognitive, emotional, and sociocultural benefits of including traditional music in the curriculum, highlighting its potential for developing creativity, critical thinking, and cultural awareness in younger students. One of the main advantages of students' passion for Uzbek folk songs is a positive impact on their cognitive development. Studies show that learning and performing traditional music stimulates a wide range of cognitive processes, including memory, attention, and language skills. Primary school students who participated in the folk music program showed improvements in memorization and hearing processing compared to their peers who did not engage in music. Methodological recommendations on the use of musical folklore in music lessons are given, which emphasize the specific use of folklore material and the main importance of taking into account the age and individual characteristics of students in the process of forming creative abilities. Folk songs play an important role in shaping the student's abilities and personality. Since folklore reflects the national character, spirituality, and worldview of the people, the spiritual and moral qualities of students are developed and improved in the process of education. Folklore reflects the linguistic capabilities of the people, their observational style, and creative power. In literature, variability is a characteristic feature of folklore, which emphasizes that folk art samples are directly related to the process of live performance, i.e., folklore works are not characterized by stagnation; they change and are updated every time they are performed, which means a high demonstration of the possibilities of artistic language. Thus, we can say that folklore is not just an example of the art of speech but also the history and culture of a people in constant motion, co-existing with it in a living state from the distant past to the present, embodying a language stock, a way of thinking, and a way of thinking. Folk songs are examples of the poetic and musical genre that have come down to our days in the oral tradition for centuries. Children's musical folklore, which is one of the main links of Uzbek musical folklore, occupies a special place in Uzbek musical culture. Because it has a special Children's world, a child's worldview, interests and aspirations, and dreams are expressed through words and melodies. In addition, the repetitive nature of folk songs combined with their rich lyrical content and distinctive melodies create an ideal foundation for memory preservation and language development of younger students. By memorizing song lyrics, learning rhythmic patterns, and understanding song structures, students engage in active learning processes that develop cognitive flexibility and problem-solving skills. Folklore is considered one of the most effective

genres in educating the national psyche, patriotic feeling, and aesthetic consciousness of a person. Along with the native language, it is necessary that each child gradually learn the language of national music. Children's musical folklore is rich and diverse in its purpose, content, compositional structure, and nature of performance. Among them there are songs for children 3-4 years old, consisting of 4 lines, as well as for older children with a large volume. Songs are performed solo, collectively, accompanied by musical instruments, or recitative.

Appeal to oral folk art opens up the possibility of preserving the centuries-old system of human values and humane relations between people in modern conditions of education of schoolchildren. The use of folklore in the classroom significantly enriches music classes and allows you to find new ways to organize lessons. The use of folklore in the classroom significantly enriches music classes, allows you to find new ways to organize lessons, helps establish good relations between students and teachers, and develops students' qualities characteristic of folk art such as variability, improvisation, collective spirituality, etc. A musical lesson based on the principles of folk art—syncretism and improvisation—most effectively develops artistic-figurative, associative thinking and imagination in the child and promotes a harmonious combination of intonation-expressive singing and plastic movements. Acquaintance with folk songs expands the understanding of the musical and poetic language of the people and its figurative and semantic structure by younger schoolchildren. The spiritual development of children is being improved, their aesthetic attitude to the surrounding reality is being brought up, and the general cultural worldview is gradually being significantly enriched. In our time, that is, in the third millennium, the task of forming the spiritual world of man and the revival and prosperity of the cultural traditions of the Uzbek people is particularly urgent. The task of developing a child's personality can be realized through music lessons, clubs, holidays, and entertainment events, and all this has a great potential for the creative development of schoolchildren. The cultural significance of Uzbek folk songs is deeply rooted in the rich history, traditions, and values of Uzbekistan. These songs serve as a cornerstone of the country's cultural identity, reflecting the diversity, resilience, and creativity of the people. Located at the crossroads of various civilizations and ethnic groups, Uzbekistan has a vibrant musical heritage characterized by a mix of local, Persian, Turkic, and Central Asian influences. Uzbek folk songs have been formed over the centuries in the dynamic interaction of various ethnic groups, religions, and historical events. The region's strategic location along the ancient Silk Road facilitated cultural exchange and

trade routes, resulting in a mix of musical styles, instruments, and lyrical themes. From the nomadic desert tribes to the urban centers of Bukhara and Samarkand, Uzbek folk songs have served as a means of preserving oral history, transmitting ancestral knowledge, and conducting collective rites and rituals. Uzbek folk songs include various themes that reflect everyday life, dreams, and spiritual beliefs of the Uzbek people. These songs are They are often divided into separate genres, such as lullabies, wedding songs, labor songs, epic narratives, and religious songs. Each genre is characterized by its own musical motifs, rhythmic patterns, and lyrical content that reflect the cultural nuances and regional variations of the colorful landscape of Uzbekistan. Because mothers sing to soothe their babies, often including gentle melodies and gentle words that evoke feelings of affection and protection. On the other hand, wedding songs accompany traditional wedding ceremonies and symbolize joy, unity, and family ties. Labor songs sung by field workers or artisans in markets are a form of rhythmic expression and collective cohesion that unites people in collective work. The universal values of folk songs develop readers' worldview and musical taste.

Thus, we can conclude that folk spoons play a very important role in the upbringing and creative development of younger schoolchildren. The greatest effect on the development of creative abilities of younger schoolchildren can be provided by: daily inclusion in the educational process of creative tasks in the field of musical folklore and exercises; performing circle or extracurricular activities according to a specially developed program. All this makes it possible to clarify and solve the problem of developing the creative abilities of younger schoolchildren through a system of creative tasks. Folk songs enrich the lives of pupils, make it more magnificent, and fill it with joys. The universal values of folk songs develop readers' worldview and musical taste. Also, universal values awaken students 'passion for national melodies and songs, foster a sense of rhythm and taste for music, foster students' sense of love for our national heritage, folk melodies, folk songs, and through them to the motherland, and develop students' skills of artistic creativity through alla, lapar, and folk songs.

References:

1. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 28.01.2022 Yildagi 2022 — 2026-Yillarga mo'ljallangan yangi O'zbekistonning Taraqqiyot strategiyasi to'g'risida Pf-60-Son Farmoni Farmoni www.lex.uz.
2. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Shavkat Mirziyoyev raisligida 2019-yil 19-mart kuni o'tkazilgan videoselektor yig'ilishidagi "Yoshlarni ma'naviyatini yuksaltirish va ularning bo'sh vaqtini mazmunli tashkil etish tog'rsida"gi

ma'ruzasida belgilab berilgan vazifalar ijrosinida minlash bo'yicha 5 ta muhim tashabbus. <https://www.pv.uz/uz/news/>

3. Alaviya M. O'zbek xalq qo'shiqlari. T., 1959

4. Ibrohimov O. " O'zbek xalq musiqa ijodi", T., 1994;

5. Zufarova.M.E Umumiy psixologiya. O'zbekiston faylasuflari milliy jamiyati nashriyoti.2010. B- 295-302

6.Sulaymonov.M. O'zbek xalq og'zaki ijodi. Namangan 2008. B-30-06

7.Теплов.Б.М Психология музыкальных способностей. Планета музыки. 2022.С-24

8. Ganiyeva, M. (2024). PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS FOR METHODOLOGICAL PREPARATION OF FUTURE ELEMENTARY SCHOOL TEACHERS FOR LOGICAL THINKING. Science and innovation, 3(B5), 178-182.

